

HOLLYWOOD'S UNORIGINALITY

by

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Hollywood's Unoriginality

Abstract

The phrase "Hollywood is out of ideas" is a common sentiment in the movie-making zeitgeist. Sequels, prequels, remakes, reboots, and spin-offs inundate the public by the entertainment industry in both film and television. This project defines originality, asks why Hollywood continually chooses to make movies that are unoriginal, and presents some solutions to this unoriginality problem. I interviewed 5 Cinema and Television Arts professors to hear their insight on if they feel a pervasive originality problem in Hollywood is present, and if they had any solutions. I received feedback from varied sources: from those that have experience in the industry, some who strictly study the industry from afar, and one who worked on the business side of the industry rather than the creative side. The last portion of the project is an original script I wrote that lacks the pitfalls Hollywood falls privy to. Because my script was motivated by a story I wanted to tell instead of Hollywood's standard of writing about what will make the most money, I tell a young girl's coming-of-age story of her overcoming the loss of her mother.

Introduction

Hollywood has become fundamentally unoriginal. The industry resorts to remakes, reboots, sequels, and franchise continuations instead of making a movie or TV show with an entirely original plot, characters, and universe. As an aspiring filmmaker, it is frustrating to consistently see these movies making up the majority of the films in the top box office, especially when I am surrounded by creative peers who make movies that every person should see. Audiences deserve to see unique content, and in turn these filmmakers should have the

opportunity to share their creativity to audiences. Knowing the creative content created by my peers on a regular basis, I know the quality of talent is not the issue, but rather what content gets selected to be made. To support this idea, let's take a look at last month's Top Box Office numbers from November 20, 2022 and see what proportion of movies are stand-alone:

Domestic Box Office For November 2022

Rank	Release	Gross	Theaters	Total Gross	Release Date	Distributor
1	Black Panther: Wakanda Forever	\$84,000,000	4,396	\$84,000,000	Nov 11	Walt Disney Studios Motion Pictures ↗
2	Black Adam	\$32,384,696	4,402	\$142,523,090	Oct 21	Warner Bros. ↗
3	Ticket to Paradise	\$18,022,945	4,066	\$50,412,445	Oct 21	Universal Pictures ↗
4	One Piece Film: Red	\$10,097,446	2,367	\$9,616,323	Nov 4	Crunchyroll ↗
5	Smile	\$7,415,192	3,659	\$101,246,517	Sep 30	Paramount Pictures ↗
6	Prey for the Devil	\$7,375,145	2,980	\$14,951,244	Oct 28	Lionsgate ↗
7	Lyle, Lyle, Crocodile	\$6,096,200	4,350	\$38,764,609	Oct 7	Sony Pictures Entertainment (SPE) ↗
8	The Banshees of Inisherin	\$3,799,218	960	\$4,632,663	Oct 21	Searchlight Pictures ↗
9	Till	\$3,798,830	2,136	\$7,420,172	Oct 14	United Artists Releasing ↗
10	Halloween Ends	\$2,518,835	3,901	\$63,894,010	Oct 14	Universal Pictures ↗

1. *Black Panther: Wakanda Forever*: sequel and part of the Marvel Cinematic Universe
2. *Black Adam*: based on the DC comic books
3. *Ticket to Paradise*: An original!
4. *One Piece Film: Red*: the **15th** feature film of the One Piece film series
5. *Smile*: An original!
6. *Prey for the Devil*: An original! (Fun fact, my father's friend wrote this film so go watch it)
7. *Lyle, Lyle, Crocodile*: originally a children's book
8. *The Banshees of Inisherin*: adapted from a play
9. *Till*: based on a true story

10. *Halloween Ends*: The **13th** movie of the *Halloween* franchise

Adding these up, 7 of the top 10 box office movies are not original And believe it or not, a 30% originality rate is circumstantially an anomaly. When I submitted my proposal for this project in December of 2021, the box office looked like this:

Top Box Office Movies

Top 20 Movies in North America - Weekend of Nov 26, 2021

This Week	Last Week	Title	Studio	Weekend Gross*	Total Gross*	Total Weeks
1	-	Encanto	Disney	\$27M	\$40.3M	1
2	1	Ghostbusters: Afterlife	Sony	\$24.5M	\$87.76M	2
3	-	House of Gucci	United Artists	\$14.23M	\$21.83M	1
4	2	Eternals	Disney	\$7.9M	\$150.64M	4
5	-	Resident Evil: Welcome to Raccoon City	Sony	\$5.28M	\$8.8M	1
6	3	Clifford the Big Red Dog	Paramount	\$4.88M	\$42.88M	3
7	4	King Richard	Warner Bros.	\$3.3M	\$11.38M	2
8	5	Dune	Warner Bros.	\$2.17M	\$102.24M	6
9	7	No Time to Die	United Artists	\$1.75M	\$158.13M	8
10	6	Venom: Let There Be Carnage	Sony	\$1.57M	\$209.52M	9

1. *Encanto*- original!
2. *Ghostbusters: Afterlife*- spin-off from the original *Ghostbusters* franchise
3. *House of Gucci*- based on real events
4. *Eternals*- part of Marvel Cinematic Universe and originally from Marvel Comics
5. *Resident Evil: Welcome to Raccoon City*- based on the Resident Evil video game franchise
6. *Clifford the Big Red Dog*- based on a series of children's books

7. *King Richard*- based on a true story
8. *Dune*- based on the book *Dune* AND a remake from 1984
9. *No Time to Die*- the **25th** movie of the James Bond franchise
10. *Venom: Let There Be Carnage*- sequel and originally from Marvel Comics

From this list, only one out of ten movies is original! Why is Hollywood lacking in creativity, and how can we solve the problem of mediocrity in the industry? This leads me to the questions I want to answer throughout the duration of this paper:

- Why does Hollywood continue to make unoriginal movies, including remakes, reboots, or films part of larger franchises?
- How can we incentivize or encourage Hollywood to start making original movies again?
- Why are these unoriginal movies still being watched by audiences?

Defining Originality- A Philosophical Struggle

Before we start answering those questions, though, we need to define what originality is. When I started this project, I went about it quite naively, thinking that *unoriginal* content and *good* content were mutually exclusive. It would be naive to say that all remakes and sequels are bad simply because they are unoriginal, just as it would be dishonest to say that all original movies are good. It is obviously more complicated than that, because there are completely original movies and television shows that are not good quality. Meanwhile, there are notable sequels and reboots that are great, or even better than the original.

Bringing this kind of nuance to the conversation can make my thesis difficult to prove.

There are two ways to define "original" in this particular discussion. The first "original" simply means that it is not based on a sequel, reboot, book, play, and so on. If it is a stand-alone movie, it is an *original* movie. However, the other definition, and I would argue, the more important definition of "original," is a work of art that is fresh, unusual, and creative. There are sequels and reboots that are original in the sense that they are unique and provide a new take on an idea, but not original because they come from an existing IP, or intellectual property. A movie can be both original and unoriginal in this sense.

On a philosophical level, though, one may be able to argue that originality simply does not exist. Every movie could be argued to be a certain creative work that already exists, but with some kind of twist. For example, this is the logline from the recent Idris Elba movie *Beast*: "A father and his two teenage daughters find themselves hunted by a massive rogue lion intent on proving that the Savanna has but one apex predator" (IMDB, 2022). Most of us read that and think, so *Jaws* but with a lion? When is adapting one intellectual property into another a lazy cash-grab and when is it getting a story out for more audiences to see? And what is the line between an homage, which is a reference to another movie, and ripping off the source material? I could go on and on about the origins of originality. But the fact of the matter is, every single piece of content from any kind of creative work- video games, books, plays, etc.- is inspired by something else. It is human nature to emulate what we find interesting. I will get into even more detail on this topic later during several of the professorial interviews. Ultimately, there is not one way to define if a stand-alone movie is truly an original one. That being said, we head back to our first definition: if it says something new and it feels like a new take, it's original.

For our purposes, we will use the following terminology for the rest of this paper:

- "Good movie:" fresh and unique

- "Bad movie:" derivative, poor storytelling, overall unenjoyable
- "Original movie:" stand-alone
- "Unoriginal movie:" sequel, remake, spin-off, and so on

Let's clarify the many types of unoriginal movies. A sequel is a continuation of a story with the same characters in the same universe. A reboot or remake is a retelling of a story that already exists, the only difference being that a reboot tends to be the terminology for TV shows and remakes for movies, but this is not a hard-and-fast rule. A spin-off is when a story lies within the same universe as another, but follows a different character or entirely new characters. A franchise is a series of movies with characters that exist all within one universe, like the Marvel Cinematic Universe.

In the spirit of this notion, I will analyze one movie of each type and where it went wrong, or right, later in this paper:

	Bad Movie	Good Movie
Original Movie	<i>Don't Worry Darling</i>	<i>Everything Everywhere All At Once</i>
Unoriginal Movie	<i>Morbius</i>	<i>Chip 'n Dale: Rescue Rangers</i>

Why is Hollywood making unoriginal movies?

Money

One obvious answer to why unoriginal movies are made is money. I must recognize that movie-making is a business, and while I would love for the most creative movies to be made, Hollywood tends to choose the movies they think will make them the most money. On the monetary side of things, Hollywood is making unoriginal movies because of streaming services competition, built-in markets, and reducing marketing costs.

According to Thompson (2016), the idea that big blockbuster movies (think almost any Marvel movie) make the most money is not the only reason that Hollywood has consistently made unoriginal movies, but rather have continued to make these movies to compete with streaming services. The rise in streaming services (including but not limited to Netflix, Hulu, HBOMax, Disney+, etc.) has introduced more original content because that content tends to be lower budget, while franchise films are a lot more expensive to make. Streaming services usually cannot afford to make these larger-budget movies. In this way, because Hollywood can fund much larger projects, it is being reinforced to almost exclusively make unoriginal sequels/franchise movies; they are the only kind of movie that people will see in theaters when they can see more original content on streaming services in the comfort of their homes. Additionally, there is something to be said about experiencing the big, loud, special effects-filled action movies in the theater versus at home. It is a better experience to see those types of movies on the "big screen." Hollywood understands this and is catering to this desire to make these flashy films that have little substance, yet are visually fun to watch.

Unoriginal films are also less likely to fail financially because of a built-in audience. According to Bilton (2017), making movies that are in some way a continuation of another

means that there is already a fan base for the movie before it is released. If the first installment did well, then the second is likely to do well also because if audiences enjoyed the first movie, they will probably want to see its sequel. For example, those that enjoyed *A Quiet Place* likely watched *A Quiet Place Part II*. Having enjoyed the characters, conflict, and world-building of the first movie, audiences will want to know what happens to the characters and plot advancement in the sequel. Reboots and sequels are sometimes referred to as "safe" movies because Hollywood knows there is a built-in market for a sequel given that its predecessor succeeded, so they are not a risky investment and are coined "safe."

The film industry is always risky. Investing more or less money into a project does not guarantee a similar multiplier of profit; if no one wants to see the movie or disliked it after having seen it, the production company will lose money. For example, the 2017 box-office bomb *Downsizing* made \$55 million at the box office but cost \$68 million to make (BoxOfficeMojo, 2017). That is a loss of \$13 million. Meanwhile, 2002's original *My Big Fat Greek Wedding* cost \$5 million to make and made over \$240 million (Vo, 2016). Now these are both examples of original films, so the volatility in profits is evident and goes to show why Hollywood continues to attempt the "safe" option; there is less risk in making something that people already know. It is worth noting based on these numbers that movie-making is *incredibly* expensive, so having a built-in audience to ensure that the production turns a profit is a major contributor to the onslaught of unoriginal movies.

Lastly, unoriginal content helps cut down on marketing costs. According to Trattner (2018), "Teaser trailers, posters, social media ads, marketing tie-ins with third parties, and other promotional efforts can add up to almost 50% of the cost of making the film." Therefore, having a film that people are already familiar with means they do not need to convince the public nearly

as much to watch it. Reducing marketing costs in turn reduces the overall cost to make the movie, so even if it fails at the box office, the production company has lost less money than if it had been a stand-alone movie. This is another way that making unoriginal movies protects Hollywood's financial standing.

Cancel Culture

We have all heard of cancel culture, but it can be tricky to define. According to Psychology Today, "Social canceling is the collective public rejection of a person, group, or organization for a perceived transgression that spreads through social media and is marked by strong negative emotional reactions and the pursuit of visible punitive actions. A core characteristic of canceling (relative to other rejections) is that to many (but not all) observers, the canceler's punitive actions appear disproportionate to the magnitude of the transgression,"

(Dholakia, 2020). See Dholakia's social canceling graphic for a more detailed process of how a person gets canceled.

While this may be controversial for some, I firmly believe that the fear of being canceled is contributing to Hollywood's unoriginality problem. It is a contributor to this excess of sequels, reboots, and so on but also is a reason that the original content being released today is uninspired and has little to say. Dholakia goes on to state, "Social canceling is not based on a balanced assessment of the transgression or any absolute criterion of wrongdoing. Because it is a visceral response and relies on one particular shared understanding of the transgression (through the lens of a political or a social ideology), one side of the story so to speak, every canceling campaign is necessarily grounded in bias." Knowing this, writers fear that they will be unable to sell a script that might offend some status quo of society, or worse, be socially ostracized in their field. Therefore, in order for them to make a living, they write about safe, inoffensive, and consequently, boring topics. This in turn produces content that is received apathetically or negatively, because it has nothing new to add to the conversation.

Production companies are also afraid to offend their audience to avoid a damaged reputation and are likely contributing to an increase in unoriginal content because it is again a "safe" project, this time in a different sense of the word. If the first installment of a film received the green-light from the public, meaning they found it non-problematic, then the sequel will likely be innocuous and safe territory as well. Writers delivering such uninspired scripts to producers for purchase may also be a factor towards their decision towards making a sequel or reboot instead of taking a chance on getting canceled with something more edgy.

Some may have doubts about how prevalent cancel culture actually is in the film industry and the world in general. A now-deleted tweet from actor, rapper, and comedian Donald Glover

(he has deleted all of his tweets for personal reasons) from notable works like *Community* and *Atlanta*, stated that "Saw people on here havin [sic] a discussion about how tired they were of reviewing boring stuff [TV and film], we're getting boring stuff and not even experimental mistakes(?) because people are afraid of getting canceled" (Kazi, 2021). A statement from such a creative person like Glover is poignant. By its strict definition, removing the profit-motive previously discussed, filmmaking is an art form. Art is supposed to make people feel uncomfortable, make comments on the current state of society, and challenge people's notions and ideas. Yet in today's social environment, people do not want to be faced with beliefs that are contrary to their own. This is creating a bottleneck for the type of content getting created, causing one-sided or agenda-based content that only satisfies a small percentage of the American audience. More open-minded audiences and move-makers would allow for a much more diverse set of films as well as more originality coming from Hollywood.

The following are some examples of cancel culture impacting the quality of a project or cancel culture affecting the public's response to a project. The first example is Warner Bros. Studios firing Johnny Depp from the *Fantastic Beasts* franchise over abuse allegations toward his ex-wife, Amber Heard. At this point, we know that the allegations were false, and in fact the opposite is true following the Johnny Depp vs Amber Heard defamation trial. Warner Bros.' reactionary response to fire Johnny Depp when the truth came out that *he* was the victim of domestic abuse in Depp and Heard's relationship punished an innocent man. Public response was reflected in the domestic Box Office numbers for the third *Fantastic Beasts* movie where Depp was replaced compared to the second where he was still involved.

- *Movie 2: Fantastic Beasts: The Crimes of Grindelwald: \$159,555,901*
- *Movie 3: Fantastic Beasts: The Secrets of Dumbledore: \$95,850,844*

This is a 40% decrease in sales, a significant number considering the project cost \$200 million to make. They did not lose money on the project due to international box office, but I showed the domestic box office because the Depp vs Heard trial was most relevant in the United States and therefore had the most impact. One may argue it is a natural decline to see each sequel reduce its profits for each succeeding movie, and this may be a contributing factor, but this is not true for the original Harry Potter series (BoxOfficeMojo.com, n.d.) or other comparable blockbuster franchises like *Twilight* (BoxOfficeMojo.com, 2012). The public's upset by Warner Bros. removal of Depp from the project led to a boycott that resulted in lower profits.

Another fairly recent example of cancel culture is Chris D'Elia's cancellation in 2020. After the actor/comedian appeared on season 2 of Netflix's *You*, allegations came out that he sexually harrassed women, some even minors. Before any legal investigation or response from D'Elia could occur however, Netflix canceled his upcoming comedy TV show with fellow comedian Brian Callen (Jackson, 2020). Once the initial outrage died down, the truth of the matter was that D'Elia cheated on his fiancée with a consenting and of-age woman because he was suffering from sex addiction. This does not excuse the moral shortcomings of cheating on one's partner, but he did nothing illegal or even reprehensible enough to cancel his show. Even if someone believes cheating on one's partner is grounds for Netflix to cancel the show, they still rid audiences of unique content that people may have enjoyed. Given that D'Elia has 3 Netflix stand-up specials, he is generally celebrated as a great comedian with something fresh and new to say. Netflix robbed audiences of a unique experience to avoid the outrage that comes from cancel culture to be directed at them rather than D'Elia.

Lastly, I will provide a personal example of how the culture's sensitivity is preventing creative ideas from getting made. A person I know, who I will refer to as "Joe" for our purposes,

is a producer who recently pitched a reality TV show about an old rap group, who all happen to be African American. The producer they were pitching to said that they liked it, but wanted there to be a little more color to it, meaning there needed to be a little more distinctiveness or energy to it. In response, Joe made a quick joke, something to the effect of "Not enough color, it's about three black guys." Now, this is a harmless joke; it is not demeaning to black people and is very lighthearted in nature.

Later, when Joe followed up with the production company on whether they were going to pick up the project, the company decided to move on with the show without them, saying that Joe's comment made one of the company's interns cry. Now, I am unclear as to whether the company bought the rights to the show so long as Joe was not a part of the project or whether the company approached the rap group themselves, stealing the idea from Joe and the people they work with. Nevertheless, this oversensitive reaction to a joke hurt Joe's livelihood and source of income. Additionally, as the producer of this potential show, Joe has a lot of insight into the details of the music group and its members. They would have particular knowledge for the show and also bring individual skill to the table as an experienced producer. The production company missed out on their insight and a potentially better show, without Joe, in the name of protecting someone's feelings. Joe was not given a chance to talk or apologize to the intern, and instead the company chose to unethically circumvent Joe because one of their interns could not take a joke.

This is not to say that all canceling is bad- the social ostracization of alleged and convicted sex offenders like Kevin Spacey and R Kelly is well-deserved; but it can quickly get out of hand and is usually not used for the good of society. In summation, cancel culture is a detriment to the creativity and boundary-pushing of Hollywood. It prevents creative work from being written, produced, and distributed for audiences to see. It also harms the lives of the actors

and filmmakers who fall victim to it, who in turn are no longer given the chance to put out creative content. In a more nuanced and communicative society in which cancel culture was replaced with conversation and understanding, more original content would flourish in Hollywood.

Incentivizing original movie-making in Hollywood

What can be done about Hollywood's unoriginality problem? One solution is for audiences to seek out independent films on their own or through intuitive apps. Another is to see if there is any financial incentive for Hollywood to take more chances on original films.

Indie Films

Ortner (2012) argues against Hollywood's happy endings and formulaic structure in favor of independent films made to be critical and realistic. Independent filmmaking has long been established as a remedy for the Hollywood blockbuster. The root of the problem is that independent media inherently reach a small audience. Because these films have a smaller budget than Hollywood's, they have little to no marketing, so people do not hear about the movie and, consequently, do not go see it. And realistically, the average person does not have time to research indie movies that are worth watching and travel to an indie theater far out of their way to see it. Instead what happens is we see commercials telling us which movies to see and, if it interests us, we go to our local theater to watch it. Again, marketing costs can reach 50% of the budget of an average Hollywood production to reach the audiences that they do, so imagine how hard it must be to get the word out about an indie film with a fraction of a Hollywood marketing budget, or even no marketing budget at all if said film's budget had to be completely allocated to other costs.

That being said, the rise of independent content on streaming services is a good alternative to having to seek out indie content in-theaters and allows a much larger audience to view them. There have been several incidents of streaming services licensing independent films so they have the chance to reach a large audience. Some notable examples of independent films that streaming services bought the rights to have on their platform are *Nomadland* and *I Am Mother* (McClintock, 2021), on Hulu and Netflix, respectively. *Nomadland* even won Best Picture at the 93rd Academy Awards in 2021, proving the potential for great quality and creativity to come out of streaming services taking chances on licensing indie films in the future (Lowry, 2021). Sometimes even on streaming services, though, the algorithms make it hard to find anything new. This is where apps are incredibly helpful.

Apps like Likewise and Taste recommend movies and TV shows they think the viewer would enjoy after they input their preferences, including independent material, for our purposes. They have an extensive database and can recommend similar indie movies or more popular movies with similar themes.

When downloading Likewise, the app asks the user to input 20 of their favorite TV shows and movies, and given that, recommends movies and shows that are similar. It indicates where the viewer can watch the film or show, so they do not have to search on multiple streaming services and apps as well. One can also search for a particular movie or show beyond the initial preferences and the app will recommend similar content. For example, I input a short indie film I enjoyed called *Fauve*, a French film about two young boys and quicksand. The app immediately gives me the film's logline, where I can watch it, ratings (which I personally ignore), and similar movies. This led me to several indie suggestions, including two called

Marguerite and *Late Afternoon*, which have similar themes as *Fauve*. This app is an empowering tool that can make it much easier to find more independent content.

Another great app for this purpose is called Taste. It asks the user to rate a number of films to understand their preferences, and then asks for the user's streaming services they currently subscribe to. With that information, the app suggests only shows and movies they might like that are on the streaming services they pay for. It is not as though it is suggesting *Stranger Things* or something equally as mainstream, though. When I tried it, it recommended shows on Netflix that I have never heard of, yet I know are available for me to watch. The app also asked me what country I live in to ensure they only recommend what's available on American Netflix. This is a great source for finding content on sites that will be accessible to the viewer without having to pay extra for it. Another possible benefit is if one watches what Taste suggests on their preferred streaming service, it may also train the site's algorithm to recommend more niche content in the future so the viewer does have to keep using third-party apps to watch what they want to.

Ultimately, a source for more creative outlets are independent films, which are said to be the antithesis of Hollywood films because they seek realism and strong themes over happy endings and apolitical narratives (Ortner, 2012). Of course, independent films inherently lack proper funding so that a lot of people can see the movie, but there is hope with apps like Likewise and Taste that help suggest what one might enjoy if their taste lies outside the mainstream.

Hollywood Taking More Chances

Is there any incentive for Hollywood to pursue more original material? The number of movie tickets sold has been in steady decline since 2002, selling 300 million tickets less in 2019

than in 2002 (Movie market summary 1995-2001, 2021). This data is from 2019 because the COVID-19 pandemic vastly affected box office sales and therefore 2020 and 2021 were not included in this study. The potential cause of this decrease is because Hollywood's mediocrity has caused people to flee to streaming services like Netflix, Hulu, DisneyPlus, and so on. Despite the decrease in ticket sales though, the actual box office numbers, or amount of money spent on tickets, has increased. This is due partly to inflation but also to a large increase in movie ticket prices, which has likely increased to compensate for the declining number of tickets sold. Because Hollywood is still making plenty of profit, though, it cannot be concluded that their lack of creativity will actually put them out of business or at least hurt the industry anytime soon. Therefore, as much as we would like to see it, Hollywood has no financial incentive to make more creative films.

Why do audiences watch unoriginal content?

Why are people still tuning into remakes and reboots- content they have basically already seen before? After all, if audiences are so unhappy with the movies Hollywood churns out, then why do people continually go to see them? Some answers include nostalgia's effect on moviegoers, giving a second chance to old movies, well-earned sequels, and loyalty to filmmakers and actors.

Nostalgia

Nostalgia "describes the bittersweet emotion that arises when we view the past with both sadness and longing" (Solomon et al, 2019). The following excerpts are from "The Power of Nostalgia," a research presentation I wrote with a team on how nostalgia influences our decision-making for a consumer behavior class. While the research centers on how to market

products to consumers using nostalgia, the research and psychology behind it are very applicable to how audiences decide to see rebooted movies originally from long ago.

Although not necessarily accurate, people view the past as "simpler times" when life was better (Sarwar, 2019). Consumers desire a "grass is greener on the other side" kind of purchase. People believe that if they buy an item that they owned when they felt happier that the item will bring them the same happiness. The thought behind seeing a nostalgic item can bring that consumer back to happier times and lead them to purchase.

(D'Ambrosio et al, 2022)

This ideology can be directly applied for our purposes; the older generations are more likely to choose to watch a film that reminds them of their childhood and brings back happy memories over the other films available to them. A recent example of this is *Top Gun: Maverick*, made 36 years after *Top Gun*. The movie relied on the nostalgia of Generation X to want to see a movie they loved when they were young (Sovar, 2022).

A critical piece of understanding nostalgia's importance lies in its psychological basis as a powerful marketing tool. The journal *Nostalgia for Early Experience as a Determinant of Consumer Preferences* by Robert M. Schindler and Morris B. Holbrook conduct a study that indicates nostalgia is involved in virtually every consumer preference. The paper references a previous study they conducted concluding that the development of tastes for entertainment products like movies and music develop at a young age, in a person's late teens and early 20s, and stays with them for much of their life. In conducting the study, they used "time-dated stimuli," or products that are identified with a narrow time frame, and used test subjects of a "product-specific age," meaning the age that the consumer

would have been at the time the product was popular. (D'Ambrosio et al, 2022)

This is obviously incredibly relevant to movie selection in addition to marketing, as the text states. It supports the idea that rebooting an old hit movie or TV show after 20 years will make those that were young during its original version want to see it.

The conclusion was that no matter what the person's age was, they preferred the music and movies from when they were young to the current music or music from before they were born. This preference, or "age-related peak" based on their age when the entertainment product was popular, remains with them throughout the rest of their lives. This creates nostalgia for the music or celebrity that they have affection for despite these no longer being popular anymore. This then implies that nostalgia exists when the product or experience in question is no longer widely accessible or available so a person has the ability to miss them. (D'Ambrosio et al, 2022)

A relevant example for our purposes is *General Hospital*. It is hard to miss the show as a whole when it has been on the air for almost 60 years over 49 seasons (imdb.com, 2022). Meanwhile, a cult classic like *Twin Peaks* was canceled after 2 seasons in 1991 and brought back for season 3 in 2017, 27 years later, because people missed it and desired a conclusion to the overarching story (Wikipedia, 2017).

From a strictly business perspective, if a filmmaker wants to reboot a show or movie from decades ago, the show should be targeted to the same generation that watched the first version. This implies that the new version will not be exactly the same as the first because the audience has gotten older, and the show must reflect that. For example, the recently rebooted animated show *Animaniacs* self-reflexively makes fun of Hollywood's recycling of movies and

shows; the irony being that the show is also a rebooted one and is therefore guilty of the same greed and unoriginality (Crandles, 2020). Even though the demographic of the show used to be kids growing up in the 1990's, now that the show has been rebooted, its audience is not still children, but those young people in the 1990s who are now grown up. In this way, the show ages with the audience, so their built-in audience base is still there. The show is also more adult in its themes as well, further proof that reboots like this one are feeding off the nostalgia of generation Z and millennials to make a profit. Preying on an audience's nostalgia in their desire to revisit the time when the original show was created makes audiences want to see said show or film.

Therefore, if I were a Hollywood producer where my job is to make the studio lots of money, I would highly encourage reboots and remakes that originally came out a decade or more ago and target the same audience who watched the original content.

A Second Try

People do not care whose idea was first; they care about whose idea was better. In Adam Grant's Ted Talk "The surprising habits of original thinkers," he found that the failure rate of companies being the first to do something is 47%, while the companies that *improved* upon existing ideas is 8% (Grant, 2016). He continues to say that "To be original, you do not have to be first, you just have to be different and better" (Grant, 2016). This is very relevant to the film industry because there are many circumstances of rebooting films that were much more positively received when remade for a new generation. Take the blockbuster sci-fi film *Dune*, for example. Based on a book and originally adapted for the screen in 1984, this version flopped and *lost* \$10 million worldwide at the box office (Box Office Mojo, n.d.). Meanwhile, the 2021 remake *made* \$236 million (Agar, 2021). This was probably due to a number of reasons, including but not limited to:

- The increasing popularity of "nerd culture" since the 1980s has made sci-fi movies like *Dune* more popular to watch
- With both movies being heavily reliant on computer-generated images (CGI), the improved special effects technology has made sci-fi more convincing and visually stimulating to watch
- The star power in the 2021 version is very recognizable and highly regarded

Giving the movie another chance given new circumstances as time goes on can be a worthwhile risk. It takes a particular eye from a filmmaker's perspective to know when a film might be ready to be told again.

A Well-Earned Sequel

Another reason that audiences are still going to see sequels or reboots is that they feel there is more story to tell about a certain character or this character deserves more opportunity to grow, done through a continuation of the story. In other words, sometimes a sequel is well-earned in that there really is more to say about their universe and the characters within it. A

"well-earned sequel" is a term I am inventing to describe sequels that deserved to be/have been made that follow a short list of criteria:

1. **The first movie leaves room for a sequel.** For a sequel to be well-earned, the first movie needs to end with plenty of questions about what might happen next, how the results of the movie's resolution will affect the characters in the future, and other intriguing loose ends. There is nothing more annoying to me when a movie leaves no loose ends but still makes a sequel, like *Cloudy with a Chance of Meatballs 2*- a silly example, but still relevant. At the beginning of the sequel, to conveniently set up its plot, there is a voiceover from Flint Lockwood, our protagonist, explaining how he's always wanted to

work for tech company Live Corp. Conveniently, this is where he ends up working a short time later (shocker!). The problem with this idea is that there is no mention whatsoever in the first movie that Lockwood's dream was to work for this company.

When a character's goals and motivations are re-written for the sake of a sequel, it feels lazy, inauthentic, and cheapens the original movie by undercutting the original movie's character motivations. It also feels incredibly cash-motivated rather than wanting to tell a fresh new story with the same beloved characters.

2. **It feels like there is more story left to be told.** When the studio behind a movie knows

there is not more to go on with a set of characters but decides to continue the franchise anyways for monetary gain, or do not care if there is no story left to tell but decide to force one anyway, a lower quality sequel almost always ensues.

An example of an infuriating franchise continuation from a film buff's perspective is *Toy Story 4*. *Toy Story 3*, by all accounts, was clearly supposed to be the final

The opening shot of *Toy Story* (1995), Andy's wallpaper:

The closing shot of *Toy Story 3* (2010), a crane-lift to the sky before fading out:

movie in the Toy Story franchise. The final shot of the movie parallels the opening shot in the first movie, as pictured (reddit.com, 2015).

This image was the perfect way to end a great trilogy, symbolic of the innocence and joy of childhood and how integral toys are a part of that. Andy gave his toys away to Bonnie who needs them more than he does, and it is a bittersweet moment of letting go of our childhoods that are so important to our identities. But then Pixar decides, for all the reasons previously discussed, to make *another* Toy Story movie, essentially nullifying the great symbolism that the third movie took care to illustrate to audiences. *Toy Story 4* was also released *nine* years after *Toy Story 3*, so it is fairly evident that they were going to retire the franchise.

3. **The first movie is enjoyable.** Of course, as my thesis dictates, a lot of sequels are bad or at least worse than the original movie. But with well-deserved sequels, the first movie needs to be well-received for the sequel to be deserved, because if an audience did not even like the first movie, why bother with a second one? Pixar's *Planes* received a 25% Rotten Tomatoes score but still decided to make *Planes: Fire and Rescue*, which made Pixar profit only \$9 million and made \$31 million less than the original movie, both domestically (BoxOfficeMojo, 2013). Especially by Disney's standards, this is an absolute failure and illustrates how forcing a second movie after the first one was bad usually ends badly financially and in audience satisfaction.

Too often, a sequel is made even when the first film does poorly, especially with franchise movies based on books. Take *The Maze Runner*, for example. Even though the movie was not received very well, they continued to make *Maze Runner: The Scorch Trials* and *Maze Runner: The Death Cure* anyways, most likely as part of a contract to make films for the entire book trilogy. Each movie had increasingly negative reviews and consequently a continually

decreasing box office (TheNumbers, 2018). The same goes for the *Divergent* trilogy and *Percy Jackson* franchise, although at least 20th Century Fox and 1492 Pictures cried uncle and canceled *Percy Jackson* production after two movies (TheNumbers, 2022). Both these franchises still turned a profit, but decreasingly so with each movie.

Now that we know what criteria meet a well-deserved sequel, let's look at a great example of it: *A Quiet Place: Part II* (spoilers ahead for both movies). At the end of *A Quiet Place*, there is a great combination of resolution and new and continued questions that welcome a new addition to the story in a genuine way.

The movie follows a family surviving an alien invasion in which the aliens do not have eyes but have incredible hearing, so to survive they must be completely silent. At the end of the first movie, the family's patriarch dies sacrificing himself for his now three children. The mother gives birth to a healthy baby, and the family figures out that the aliens' only weakness is to overwhelm their ears with feedback from loudspeakers. This overwhelming noise opens up their "ears" in a way that exposes flesh, a vulnerability to an otherwise impenetrable exoskeleton,

which allows them to shoot the aliens and kill them. The final shot of the first movie is of the mother cocking a shotgun, empowered by being able to kill the creatures.

Despite this discovery, there are still many questions left to be answered, which satisfies the first and second criteria. During the climax of the film the aliens essentially destroy their home trying to find and kill them. Where will they go now? How much harder will it be to survive now that they have lost the father of the family and simultaneously gained a new member of the family, a baby that cannot be told to be quiet? There are many unanswered questions that the movie develops as the plot progresses; it is not as if these questions were there from the beginning and were unsatisfyingly unanswered just so a second movie could be made. There is still much story to be told with these new challenges they are presented by the time the first movie comes to a close. The third criteria is also met; *A Quiet Place* was incredibly well-received, deemed an incredibly inventive horror film by doing what most horror movies fail to do; have characters the audiences care about and root for. The biggest reason this movie works is that it is first and foremost about the characters, not the aliens or the scary situation they are in. Writer and director John Krasinski described the movie as a "a love letter" to his kids and the extremes that every parent would go to protect them (Farrand, 2020). Ultimately, there are instances where a sequel is a welcomed continuation to see how beloved characters progress through their story. This is a perfectly acceptable form of "unoriginal" content. However, I would argue that the majority of modern sequels do not pass these criteria and contribute to Hollywood's unoriginality problem.

Creator Loyalty

Another reason that audiences continue to watch unoriginal content is because we live in a culture where fame and celebrities are highly regarded. Many people will watch any movie as

long as a certain actor is in it or if it was directed by a particular person. There is a reason why in movie trailers or posters they will boast "from the producers who brought you *The Hunger Games*" or put all the notable actors' names in huge font so they cannot be missed. Then people think, "Well I liked *The Hunger Games*, so I guess I'll like this movie too and go see it," or "Oh, I love Leonardo DiCaprio, so I'll see anything with him in it" respectively. This does not guarantee that the content will be good; however, the loyalties built through parasocial relationships like this are part of the built-in audience of an unoriginal movie as discussed earlier. A parasocial relationship is a "one-sided relationship that a media user engages in with a media persona" (Vinney, 2022). Whether we can admit it or not, there is a part of many of us who not only want to meet the celebrity that draws us in, we want them to like us; we want to be like them. This kind of loyalty is a contributing reason to big-name actors being paid so well, because productions understand that attaching this actor with the project is essentially guaranteed to bring the movie more money.

Professorial Interviews

For the next stage of my research, I thought it necessary to interview Cinema and Television Arts professors at California State University, Fullerton (CSUF). With each professor having very different knowledge on the topic at hand based on their relationship to the entertainment industry, each interview had very diverse views on the following questions I asked:

- Are there differences in working on mainstream, high-budget movies versus indie movies?
- What is Hollywood's attitude towards the content they choose to make?

- How does profit motive conflict with trying to make a quality product?
- Do you think there is a fundamental originality problem with Hollywood?
- Do you have any other insight related to this subject?

Interview 1: Rebecca Sheehan

My first interview was with Professor Rebecca Sheehan, a critical studies professor who specializes in experimental cinema. Because her focus is on movies that break the mold and are exclusively independent, I valued her insight on the current landscape of unoriginal content. Her thoughts on mainstream television are that despite the rise in television reboots, some of the best innovations we are seeing right now are in TV. She believes the cause may be because TV is less of an investment from production companies compared with a high-budget movie. With TV programs, the company loses less money if the show does not prove to be popular. Examples of these groundbreaking programs in terms of aesthetics, genre, and sound design are *Big Little Lies* and *Euphoria*, where the set design is highly stylized, and the creators combine genres to put an original spin on stories.

On the topic of unoriginality in a general sense, Sheehan mentioned an interesting anecdote about a professor she had in grad school who refused to ever punish a student for plagiarizing in her class; she believed that originality simply did not exist. Sheehan's professor would assert that everything is stolen from something else. Though Sheehan believes it is an extreme to view everything new as something plagiarized, she does feel there should be consequences for literally copying and pasting someone else's work. And she does acknowledge that her professor's view is an interesting thought experiment about what originality means, and also helped me dictate how I discussed originality earlier on in the paper.

In regards to our more general discussion, Sheehan remarked that financial gain has a critical impact on the development of ideas. She stated, "There is a monopoly on the marketplace of ideas in Hollywood determined by the financial incentive to corner and serve a limited audience," (Sheehan, 2022). Sheehan goes on to note that Hollywood's lack of diversity of ideas has much more dire consequences than just the production of unoriginal content. She hypothesizes that Hollywood's narrowness is harmful to our democracy. Because so much of our ideologies come from entertainment, a media landscape controlled by very few people with the same ideologies leads to little political diversity. Hollywood is known for being very liberal-leaning, so conservative viewpoints are being underrepresented and will continue to be as Hollywood becomes increasingly monopolistic. Our concern as Americans is the consolidation of power over what gets made and seen. For example, the rise in streaming services, and specifically original content made on those platforms, is consolidating all three major steps in the industry: production, distribution, and exhibition. In other words, Netflix is now able to make the movie, advertise the movie, and offer the movie on their app, which leads to a stifling of certain viewpoints and the bolstering of others- a practice contrary to one of America's core values of freedom of speech, along with an open exchange of ideas and beliefs.

Sheehan's solution to this issue is that the government should intervene and work to break up these monopolies and prevent big tech mergers because there is too much at stake in terms of the marketplace of ideologies. She remarked that "monopolies are about unoriginality" because they prevent access to new ideas (Sheehan, 2022). Ultimately, it would be beneficial for America's democracy and the creativity of the film and TV industry if the largest production companies were prevented from completely taking over the market and controlling the country's culture and thinking.

Interview 2: Shelley Murray

My second interview was with Professor Shelley Murray, who has experience in the TV industry and is a former Academy of Arts and Sciences interviewer. She now teaches several television classes at CSUF. Murray thinks that the root of the problem with unoriginal TV shows is the lack of diversity in the people who are in charge of TV pitch meetings (Murray, 2022). A pitch meeting is where a person presents their TV show or movie ideas to a group of producers who then decide if they want to pursue the idea at their production company. It can be thought of as the bottleneck where ideas are filtered from the masses and made into the content we all see. The problem, Murray remarked, is if these producers do not understand the story you are pitching, they will make a person's story something that they understand. In other words, if producers do not find the pitch relatable because they do not come from the same culture or background, and therefore do not know if it will make money, the producers then alter the pitch into something they understand. This situation can mean that producers will only buy the pitcher's idea if they can change the premise or core of the show altogether. The ideas that get greenlighted then are unoriginal because they are filtered through the same few people whose mindset and life experience remain unchanged.

When trying to make a pitch seem more desirable and have a greater chance at being successful, a pitcher will say that their show "is like show A meets show B." "It's *Friends* meets *The Office*," for example. It is a way to show producers that the show will be successful, because it is similar to previously successful shows. So even in selling a person's individual idea, it is common and encouraged to relate it to previous shows or intellectual properties (IPs). This brings into question again, where do we draw the line on what can truly be deemed original?

Murray shared with me her experience with pitching a show. Her premise was about a father who passed away and left his construction business to his daughter, rather than his son. The son is more of a screw-up and would be unable to handle running a business and the daughter is more responsible, which is why the father left the business to her. But by the end of the pitch meeting, the producers wanted to change the premise to the son inheriting the business and the daughter assisting him in some way, which completely changes the inherent conflicts within the story about a woman leading in a male-dominated field and the struggles that come with that position. Murray declined to sell the script with these changes, and to interject my own feelings, I am glad she did. Hearing this story frustrated me, how having a carefully crafted script, written with great thought, consideration, and passion can be eviscerated and altered so quickly by producers that think their version might sell better.

When discussing Hollywood's unoriginality as a whole, Murray remarked that different forms of intellectual property have been made into other forms of media for a very long time. Famous plays in the 1800s were adapted from previously written books. The reason it feels like TV has almost exclusively been rebooting shows in recent years is because TV has not been around as long as movies, books, plays, and so on. In other words, the cycle time on when an old show has been far enough removed from people's minds that it can be remade is a lot sooner than with other forms of media.

For example, the movie *Little Women* has been made 5 times, with the most recent 2 remakes 25 years apart from each other (pbs.org, 2020). This gap in time allows for a whole new generation to enjoy the newest version and to watch a new interpretation of it. But TV shows have a much smaller cyclical remake period. The rebooted *iCarly* began in 2021 while the original show ended in 2012. This is only 9 years of being off the air before coming on again.

That means the same generation who watched the original is watching the reboot, and it has not been long enough for there to be a new twist to it (Wikimedia Foundation, 2022). With the short turnaround, it feels like every new show coming out is a remake of some kind because, with television being one of the newest forms of media, rebooted content to draw on is simply not as old as drawing from movies, plays, etc. It was not until the early 1950s that a television became a household object, so with less than 100 years to draw on, television is almost in its infancy when compared to plays and books (Daisy, 2018). Ultimately, people will keep adapting IPs into other forms of media, and Murray believes that soon enough new mediums will be developed.

Another way to help Hollywood's creativity problem, Murray noted, is for smaller, creative movies to get more notice. This can be done if small films manage to get nominated for a Golden Globe, Screen Actors Guild Award, or even an Oscar. These nominations help to get the movie out in the public eye. Rather than there being a lack of creative content, as discussed before, there is an inability for these stories to get mainstream notice. However, if the filmmakers behind these films submit their film to every possible film awards and festival, the film will gain popularity and increase its viewing with the general public.

The last thing we discussed is the contradiction between film being treated as an art or as a business. It is impossible to have one without the other for a film to succeed. At the same time, one or the other is going to suffer because they act as opposing forces. This perpetual struggle means that successful movies from a business perspective are not as successful in terms of artistry, like the Marvel franchise. On the opposite spectrum, the creative pieces are not well-funded, so they succeed in creativity but do not make much or any money. All art in commerce faces this; the never-ending battle that frustrates the creatives and business people alike.

Interview 3: Ari Posner

My third interview was with Professor Ari Posner. One of our main points of discussion was that having a higher budget for a film or program does not necessarily mean that the project's outcome will be better or more creative.

Professor Posner also worked in the TV industry. Some of his notable works include writing for the 2000s sitcom *Reba* and producing the 2015 FX show *Married*. With industry experience, Posner has learned that there is a pecking order based on how long or how successful a person has been in the industry, so those that are just starting out have little to no influence on what programming can get made. He noted that the leverage a person has to push limits on the content that gets created is based on how much power they have in the industry. The exception to this unspoken rule is that new writers starting out may be given a chance by producers because those new to the industry will agree to sell their script for cheaper than those more established. This creates a low-risk, high-reward scenario for the producers because if the pilot tanks, they have not spent much money on it; but if it succeeds, they will turn a tremendous profit.

Posner expanded on Professor Murray's opinion by adding that having any proof of concept will make it more likely for producers to buy a script. This can mean building proof of concept in unique ways, like making the show themselves and posting it to YouTube. Producers want some kind of insurance that will make them feel more comfortable with putting their money on the line, so a new writer should try to develop unique ways of building proof of concept for a better chance at success. For example, the HBO series *Insecure* started out as a YouTube series called "The Mis-Adventures of Awkward Black Girl & Friends" under Issa Rae's production company, Hoorae Media. Issa Rae created her own proof of concept when she made YouTube videos that proved she was funny, relatable, and could draw in an audience. While this

number may be much higher because viewers found the video after *Insecure* came out, the first episode of "The Mis-Adventures of Awkward Black Girl & Friends" has almost 3 million views, proving that it was enjoyable to people and a contributing factor to getting the show green-lighted (Rae, 2011). This is all evident that it takes perseverance to get one's voice heard.

When asked if originality can exist in the film industry, Posner remarked that when it comes to creating an original show or film, "originality comes in how you adapt it, write it, and cast it," (Posner, 2022). Posner focused on bringing a fresh take to a common concept. For example, a lot of shows are about family, but the situation they are in, the cast of characters that are written, the actors' abilities, and so on is what makes each family comedy different.

Interview 4: Heather Osborne-Thompson

My next interview was with Dr. Heather Osborne-Thompson, who teaches several television classes at CSUF and has many publications on a wide range of television topics. One of the concepts we talked about was what defined originality. Just because a show or movie is not original in that it is a sequel or reboot, does not mean that it is unoriginal in terms of its storyline and narrative. A piece being derivative or not is a false binary; every writer is influenced by other written works so essentially nothing can be wholly original. Therefore, it is not a fair assumption that an original work is good, and a derivative one is automatically bad.

Our next topic was discussing the high barrier to entry for independent films into mainstream movie theaters. Within franchises, the attempt to create cohesion across each movie helps perpetuate its prominence, which crowds the market from more original films entering. She refers to the Marvel/DC/Superhero movies as "big, fat, loud movies" and how they are franchised in a way to remain relevant (Osborne-Thompson, 2022). When these movies and shows are developed, not only the main character's universe is kept in mind, but the universe of

the whole franchise as well. In the Marvel franchise's 2021 Disney Plus show *Hawkeye*, for a person to have completely understood the plot and who the characters are, an audience member would have also needed to watch 3 other movies in the franchise. The first movie is *Black Widow*, which one would need to see to know who the Black Widow assassin, Yelena Belova, is as well as at minimum *The Avengers* and *Avengers: Endgame* to understand who Hawkeye is and his journey mourning his good friend, Natasha Romanoff (IMDB, 2021). By building movies and shows that incorporate the characters from the surrounding universe, yet are not necessarily the focus, Marvel is able to keep themselves in people's minds like no other franchise.

Interview 5: Garrett Hart

My final interview was with Garrett Hart, Professor and Department Chair of Cinema and Television Arts. Professor Hart ran Paramount Picture's content development from 1993 through 2004. In this role, writers would pitch him an original idea and several would be purchased. Then they would decide from there which scripts would move on to actually be filmed as a pilot. During this period of time, buyers were looking for material that would "break through," or have an edge that would make a script more purchasable, and this edge could be found by using a known commodity. As discussed, this can be something like "my show is *The Office* meets *Stranger Things*."

The issue is not a lack of creativity, but the need for a built-in hook for marketers to sell a program easier. Netflix is dropping about 370 titles this year (Joseph, 2022). The amount of content is overwhelming! No one can watch all of that content, so marketers need a way to grab the public's attention so they will watch their show. A good way to do that is to make content people are already familiar with.

From a business standpoint and as a former producer, Professor Hart recommends to networks and production companies that they buy the rights to IPs so they can be made into a show or movie later on because that is what is profitable right now. To start our interview, Hart said to me "Just because something is repeated, does not mean that it is inherently worse," (Hart, 2022). While Hart does feel like some of the heart and magic of the industry with classic movies like *ET* has been lost nowadays, he overall does not feel that there is an over-reliance in film and TV on redoing things. Hart warns how the categorization of originality should be defined in this paper, and he urged me to develop the nuance on Hollywood's recycling that I have meticulously attempted to do. Especially since, as we know, drilling down far enough will show that content will almost always be derivative of something else.

Another premise he made me rethink was my thoughts on how the top ten box office films were mostly part of a franchise, sequel, or derivative of another IP. This does not mean that there are no unoriginal theatrical releases! Instead, it shows how they do not reach the top 10 because of a lack of name recognition/familiarity. In other words, if we are really in the market for a unique movie, scroll down to what number 59 is on the box office and we may find great new content there. It is in some respects a positive way of thinking about the box office and my topic as a whole. If the top 10% of the box office is very derivative, we can see the glass as 90% full rather than 10% empty by seeking out the movies lower on the list that are more independent. While it would be unrealistic to list the other 90 films of the November 2022 box office, scrolling through all 91 movies listed showed me a large handful of films that I had never heard of before. This gives me hope that indie content is more prevalent than I thought, and this entire struggle feels less hopeless than it did at the beginning of my journey conducting this thesis.

From the Source: Recent Examples of Movies of All Kinds

As mentioned, I wanted to review a good original, good unoriginal, bad original, and bad unoriginal movie to describe and analyze what makes the movies good or bad, and original or unoriginal. My chosen movies have been released as recently as possible, all in from 2022, to prove the relevance and volume of each type of movie. In other words, I could have discussed *The Godfather Part II* as a good unoriginal movie for being a famous example of a sequel that was as good, if not better than, the original *The Godfather*. However, I wanted to pick movies that you, the reader, may have seen recently to connect more with the material, and that are also fun for me to talk about. Spoilers ahead for all four movies I discuss.

Good Unoriginal: *Chip 'n Dale: Rescue Rangers*

Chip 'n Dale: Rescue Rangers is a good example of a remake that subverts expectations in a way that makes a reboot with the same characters interesting and new. The film reuses old intellectual property of Disney in a modern take. They make meta references to the idea that for the characters, the original Chip 'n Dale show was just a show for them as well, and they are actors even though they are animated

characters. This is a meta, or self-referential, commentary on the idea that cartoons live in the real world and exist beyond our screens; they are sentient and this subverts our expectations on how we think about animated characters.

Before we dive into the story, see the poster to the right's tagline, "It's not a reboot. It's a comeback." The poster self-reflexively makes note that this is not an original movie, but it posits a reflective nod of understanding that reboots have been increasingly frequent. This movie does not want to be labeled as such and with the same connotations that it will be a simple cash-grab.

The story goes that Chip and Dale have not seen each other since the ending of their show and have had a falling out. Since then, Dale has gotten "CGI" surgery to be computer animated instead of hand-drawn, which is the only style of animation that existed when the original show came out. He claims that he had it done to "get more roles," since most animation done today is computer-generated. While played off as a funny joke, the film is being self-referential about animation's evolution since the popularity of the original show.

The film's central conflict centers on Chip and Dale reuniting to save one of their old co-stars, Monterey Jack. Jack has been kidnapped by Peter Pan, who has become a mob-esque boss who uses an evil machine to turn animated characters into bootleg versions of other characters and force them to act in terrible bootleg films. The machine, depicted below, is essentially extreme plastic surgery for animated characters; it changes the types of ears they have or gives them a different number of fingers, depending on the films they will be forced to bootleg. The film is focusing its conflict on the bad people who steal other ideas from people and make their own version at a poorer quality. The movie, as a reboot, is making fun of other reboots and the creators behind them for being lazy, cheap, and uncreative for the sole purpose of profit.

I would consider *Chip 'n Dale: Rescue Rangers* a good unoriginal movie because it develops an entirely new angle on these existing characters while still serving as a great homage to the original show. We see a different relationship between the chipmunks from the original show, a falling out from creative differences and a rekindling of their friendship over the bond to save their former co-star. They still stay true to the themes of the show, however. As Gadget Hackwrench says in episode 47, she refers to the rescue rangers as "a small but efficient battalion of do-gooders devoted to helping those in trouble." The film being centered around busting a crime syndicate is a fresh and creative way to reboot a show that was about saving the day and helping people in their community.

Good Original: *Everything, Everywhere All At Once*

Widely regarded as the perfect movie for optimistic nihilism- the idea that nothing matters, but be kind anyways- *Everything Everywhere All At Once* is an absurdist comedy-drama about multiversal travel and generational healing. The movie was written and directed by Daniel Kwan and Daniel Scheinert. Often working together, they are affectionately referred to as "Daniels."

The film follows laundromat owners Evelyn and Waymond Wang, who are being audited for their business. During this process at the IRS building, Evelyn is recruited to save the multiverse from an evil force, Jobu Topaki, who is destroying each universe one at a time. Evelyn must go through the process of “verse jumping” to fight Jobu, where she taps into a version of herself in another universe to learn the skills that she has in that universe. Jobu, meanwhile, can seamlessly “verse jump” throughout all universes and is, therefore, incredibly powerful. Because she can do this, though, she experiences every single universe at the same time, experiences every reality, and sees every single possibility in existence, which has led her to feel that life is meaningless and nothing matters. So, she created the everything bagel, a black hole that destroys everything within it. Jobu wants to enter into it to finally find peace and stop experiencing everything, everywhere, all at once.

The reason I love this movie and find it to be a good one is because it does what most modern sci-fi fails to do; use sci-fi as a metaphor for philosophical discussion and interpersonal conflict. It turns out that Jobu Topaki is Evelyn and Waymond's daughter, Joy, from another universe. In the original IRS-auditing universe, Evelyn and Joy's relationship is very strained.

Evelyn is disappointed in her daughter for being gay and having little direction in life. The movie serves as a great metaphor for how even though life pushes and pulls us in a thousand different directions, there are still choices that each person makes that make a difference- like how every small decision made branches into a new universe. Despite the feeling that nothing matters and it is all just noise, we can still *choose* to be kind. Waymond does not fully understand the gravity of the Jobu Topaki situation because Evelyn was called on to save the multiverse, but he still begs for all the fighting to stop, pleading that "The only thing I do know is that we have to be kind." This appeal is how Evelyn gets through to her daughter. Instead of fighting Jobu Topaki, she convinces her that life is worth living.

There is beautiful parallelism between Jobu wanting Evelyn to physically release her so she can go into the bagel in one universe, and the IRS-universe-Joy wanting her mother to let her go figuratively because they have never gotten along and should just go their separate ways. But in both universes, Evelyn convinces Joy that "no matter what, I still want to be here with you." Joy pleads with Evelyn that "Here we only get a few specks of time where any of this actually

makes any sense," to which Evelyn replies "Then I will cherish these few specks of time." Evelyn's journey taught her there is always an upside, always something to love and appreciate. And as the movie jokes, even in a universe that seems completely pointless, like one where everyone has hotdogs for fingers, that universe learned to get really good with their feet.

I have great respect for the people who made this movie. According to IMDB (2022), "All the VFX for this film was done by 9 people, including the two directors, with the majority of the shots being done by a core group of 5 people. None of the VFX team went to school for VFX. They were all friends who taught themselves with tutorials they found online for free." It is proof that a great movie does not need a huge team of people working on it; it needs passion and a love for filmmaking that the "Daniels" and their team possess.

On the topic of originality, multiverse movies have been done before, but it is in the unique way that it is approached, and how they use the multiverse to comment on human nature and interaction that makes this movie both breathtaking and heart wrenching to experience.

Bad Original: *Don't Worry Darling*

If I had to describe *Don't Worry Darling* in two words, it would be: missed opportunity. The drama film directed by

Olivia Wilde follows a young woman leading a peaceful life in a 1950s experimental community until she realizes that it is not what it seems. Alice begins having disturbing visions and experiencing unsettling things in her community that make her feel as if something is wrong. While preparing dinner for her husband, Jack, she cracks an egg, but there's nothing inside of it. She cleans the house and the walls close in on her, then pop back into place like nothing was wrong. All is not right, and when she tells Jack about these occurrences, he does not believe her. The problem with this story-wise? This is the entire first and second act of the movie. For about 1 hour and 30 minutes, something weird happens and then she gets gaslighted by everyone around her telling her that everything is fine.

It is not until act 3 of the film, with 30 minutes left, that we find out that this entire community, the Victory Project, is actually a simulation and Jack, her ex-boyfriend in real life, kidnapped her and forced her into this world where they can be together and live the "perfect" life. Jack leaves the simulation during the day, under the guise of him going to work in the simulation, but Alice and all the other women in the community are brainwashed and trapped within it. The overall commentary of the film is supposed to show the danger of incels and people who fall victim to echo chambers of harmful ideas, yet it does not land at all because we only get to witness the result of this scenario for a few minutes of screen time. Additionally, it turns out that all of the weird visions she was seeing was her subconscious trying to poke through to tell her that this world is not real, and the weird things happening to her were all simulation malfunctions.

Once Alice figures all this out by remembering her real life while inside the simulation, she inevitably kills Jack in the simulation which also kills him in real life. This is an entirely unsatisfying death because she does so accidentally in self-defense so he would stop embracing

her while pleading for her forgiveness after all he had done to her. In a movie that is supposed to be a commentary on women's oppression and incels needing to learn the error of their ways, it is insane not to give Alice the redemption arc to kill him intentionally for the horrendous crimes he has committed against her.

Taking a step back from that, though, why would killing someone in a simulation kill them in real life? The definition of a simulation is "the imitation of the operation of a real-world process or system over time" (Wikipedia, 2022). An *imitation* of real life heavily implies that what happens within it will not affect the person outside of it. It really felt like the "if you die in the game, you die for real" cheesiness from the 2006 film *Stay Alive* that was ridiculed by audiences and has since become a publicly mocked trope. It is still used quite frequently, like in 2017's *Jumanji*, except *Jumanji* is a comedy and *Don't Worry Darling* is supposed to be taken seriously. Using this trope pulled me out of the story entirely. Despite that, if Olivia Wilde decides that in her movie, dying in simulations kills you in real life, fine, but that does not excuse the lazy writing for *why* he is killed. It is a cheap and convenient way for Alice to be safe once she escapes the simulation- so that Jack would not be there in the real world to put her right back into the simulation, rendering this whole redemption arc meaningless.

Another issue I take with this film earlier on is when Alice accidentally stumbles upon the simulation's exit without understanding what it is. She puts her hands on it and passes out, only to wake up back in bed at the Victory Project. Later though, we know that this is the actual exit from the simulation that she escapes through at the movie's conclusion. So why did she not wake up in the real world the first time she visited it? It would have been incredibly more horrifying if she woke up, remembered everything, and then Jack somewhere gets notified by the Victory Project's king pin that she is free and puts her back in the simulation by force. Alice

would then be back under the simulation's spell, forgetting everything that just happened and being oblivious to this world not being real. The audience would be on the edge of their seat, rooting for her to remember the truth again and escape this prison she is trapped in.

The reveal about the Victory Project being a simulation is also riddled with logistical plot holes. Are family members and police not looking for Alice? We find out that in the real world she is a surgeon. She is then missing out on surgeries she was expected to complete, so the police would definitely be looking for her, and Jack would be a suspect as her ex-boyfriend, especially since he is probably also missing in the eyes of the law to avoid being found with Alice, as pictured above. We are not given an answer to this question though because, again, this sequence is rushed and we only get about 5 minutes of seeing the real world. While it may seem like Wilde did this to make the simulation feel more real and frightening because it encapsulated Alice's whole world, from a storytelling perspective it is lazy to leave common sense questions like these unanswered.

While researching more about the movie, I found a commentary video discussing how preliminary drafts of the script made Jack's death a murder rather than an accident and made his character more of an asshole to fit the incel description. The movie's potential for greatness was there, but because it was re-written, it completely missed the mark. There is speculation that because Harry Styles, beloved pop star, played Jack, his publicists and those in charge of his image refused to let him play an unlikeable character. This sends a lot of mixed messages about how we are meant to view incels and makes us question the film's casting. Quite famously, Styles was in a relationship with Wilde during the movie's production, implying nepotism was a factor.

Another possible contribution to the movie's negative reactions was that Wilde emphasized that she wanted the movie to encapsulate female desire rather than male desire, because most movies focus on male pleasure. This leads to several sexual scenes between Alice and Jack, where her pleasure is the focus. However, this is not the right movie to shine a light on this topic. As we know, Alice is in the simulation against her will, so this simulation sex is essentially rape, which entirely sends the wrong message that Wilde was intending. Therefore, while watching those scenes, it might feel empowering at the time, but once it is revealed that everything is a simulation, it leaves a sour taste in one's mouth.

Ultimately, this movie had an originally intriguing idea that was an absolute mess in execution. Filled with frustrating plot holes and horrible pacing, the film's interesting premise quickly becomes incredibly disappointing and never pays off. The film's first act drags on for too long for the sole purpose of showing off all the creepy ways they can show the audience that something is wrong, and the third act of Alice's discovery of the simulation and escape is entirely rushed and unsatisfying. The casting, writing, and editing all contributed to the film's downfall and illustrate how a good concept or intended message alone does not make a good movie.

Bad Unoriginal: *Morbius*

Since I have been picking on the Marvel franchise throughout this paper, I thought it only right to continue to mock them in a review of their 2022 film *Morbius*. The antihero origin movie directed by Daniel Espinosa was ridiculed by the internet for being so bad and made into so many memes that Sony decided to re-release the film months after its initial opening to capitalize on its virality (Guy, 2022). The run time of a little over 90 minutes illustrates, before even watching the film, that it is rushed and incomplete.

The film is about a doctor named Michael Morbius, who is cursed with a blood disease that has yet to be cured- so he has set out to cure it by injecting vampire bat DNA into him. While this experiment heals his disease, it also causes him to turn into a vampire-like beast hungry for human blood. Upon his initial transformation, he unknowingly kills multiple people and drains them of their blood. When his benefactor and best friend Milo, who is afflicted with the same disease, finds out about his experiment's success, he refuses to believe that it will be more of a curse than a blessing, and injects himself with it too.

Suddenly Milo, a kind and generous man who lived with a debilitating disease his entire life, becomes our villain the second he has the strength to kill people. Milo begins to suck the blood from people at random, ravaging New York City. Morbius goes after him and eventually

kills his best friend of over 20 years. The post-credit scene, standard in Marvel films, desperately tries to tie Morbius into the Spiderman universe, given that in the original comics Morbius is a Spiderman villain.

Now, if you are thinking that that was a very short summary of the film, that is because the film is so incredibly inane that there is not a lot to say about it. But the major problem with the film is that it does not make any sense. Morbius is a doctor, a man with a conscience who proclaims that once he takes care of Milo, he is going to figure out how to reverse his condition so he does not hurt anyone else. But the immediate scene after Milo's death is the post-credit scene wherein Morbius agrees to help fight Spiderman and become a bad guy. Why? That is completely contrary to his motivations throughout the entire film and undercuts his entire moral qualms with killing people against his will. It is laughably stupid and makes the entire film feel pointless.

Milo becoming the villain of the story is nonsensical, forced, and rushed. There is a flashback scene of him being bullied because of his illness as foreshadowing for him wanting revenge once he gets his supernatural abilities. But given their friendship, it makes no sense that he refused to believe Morbius that he should not inject himself with the vampire bat DNA. Why would Milo believe that his lifelong friend would try to harbor for himself the only antidote to their shared disease? It is simply lazy writing.

The effects are also uninspired and not anything interesting to watch. As pictured below, Morbius' vampire-like abilities give him super speed, so they illustrate that with black smoke movement all around Morbius anytime he moves. It is boring and not very engaging to look at, as I am sure was intended.

Ultimately, mediocrity prevails. Sony clearly did not care about honoring a great Marvel Comics villain or putting a new spin on an existing story. Marvel/Sony wanted to make money and knew they could do that by putting the Marvel stamp on a lackluster film.

Conclusion

There are many answers to the question, “Why has Hollywood become so unoriginal?” that stem from every aspect of the entertainment industry, from pre-production through post-production and beyond. Within Hollywood as an institution, if there is more diversity of life in those involved in pitch meetings, more creative content will be greenlit. A shift in the current culture of Hollywood may also make filmmakers feel more comfortable to challenge society through their films without fear of social ramifications.

Additionally, films that have been previously made have a built-in audience that aids in earning a profit. The increase in movie ticket prices and rise of streaming services have also forced Hollywood to make big blockbuster, yet unoriginal, films to draw in their audiences.

Unoriginal movies also tend to succeed because of the nostalgia that movies that have already been made provide for viewers or because some sequels are well-deserved.

While originality is incredibly hard to define and can be different for every person, some solutions to Hollywood's unoriginality are to seek out independent films and to stop seeing the films that Hollywood thinks we as an audience want to see. Apps like Likewise and Taste can help audiences find original content. Finally, eliminating monopolies on production companies and allowing all movies to enter and win notable film-making awards.

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